

Original Research

Kuznets Curve Hypothesis: New Evidence from Comparison of E-Waste and Carbon Dioxide Kuznets Curves

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Abstract

Although the empirical literature on the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) is well-established for carbon dioxide emissions, it remains relatively limited for other forms of pollution, particularly electronic waste. This study reviews the existing literature on the Kuznets Curve and tests the EKC hypothesis for two types of pollution; electronic waste and carbon dioxide emissions. For this purpose, the Feasible Generalized Least Squares (FGLS) method was applied to data from 28 European countries over the period 2002-2020, based on available statistical data. The findings confirm the EKC hypothesis for both pollution types. The estimated threshold for electronic waste is \$89,267.68, while the threshold for carbon dioxide emissions is \$64,622.64, which is lower than the threshold for electronic waste. Consequently, the threshold for electronic waste occurs at a higher GDP per capita compared to carbon dioxide emissions, indicating that the harmful effects of electronic waste are still not fully understood or addressed. Additional results suggest that ICT exports, economic structure, and governance have contributed to the reduction of electronic waste, while technological development and population growth have increased it. In contrast, technological progress and population growth have reduced carbon dioxide emissions, while ICT exports and economic structure have contributed to rising air pollution. The main recommendation of this study is the international commitment to implement standards that reduce all types of pollution in all economic and social dimensions.

Keywords: Carbon dioxide, electronic waste, environmental Kuznets curve, Europe.

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Introduction

Energy consumption is essential for production and economic activities (Yuan et al., 2008; Anwana & Akpan, 2016; Bayat et al., 2017; Haseeb et al., 2019; Saudi et al., 2019; Das et al., 2019). Meanwhile, the non-linear relationship between energy consumption and economic growth (Moon & Sonn, 1996, Lee & Chang, 2007; Antonakakis et al., 2017; Muhammad, 2019) and the relationship between resource consumption, particularly fossil fuels, and environmental degradation (Bloch et al., 2012; Omri, 2013; Abdel-Gadir, 2020) indicate that the goals of energy policies, including energy security, environmental sustainability, and economic development, are sometimes inconsistent with one another (Jordan-Korte, 2011). In this regard, various studies have demonstrated that GDP leads to an increase in CO₂ emissions and environmental pollution (Teng et al., 2021; Ahmed et al., 2020; Umar et al., 2020; Lingyun Zhang et al., 2021). For instance, Adams and Klobodu (2018) argue that the economic growth of African countries has come at the expense of environmental damage. They also note that the rate of economic growth is linked to varying levels of environmental instability: higher economic growth rates are associated with greater environmental instability, while lower or zero growth rates are linked to greater environmental stability (Antonakakis et al., 2017). On the other hand, some economists believe that the decoupling of economic growth from natural resources is possible by applying policies and creating appropriate institutions (Schandl et al., 2016; Szigeti et al., 2017). Policies aimed at improving productivity, saving energy, and promoting human capital and innovation to address energy poverty have led developed countries to be less inclined to consume energy per unit of production compared to poorer countries (Mahmood & Ahmad, 2018; Ziolo et al., 2020).

Kuznets' initial hypothesis revealed an inverted U-shaped relationship between per capita income and income inequality (Kuznets, 2019). He argues that the transition from pre-industrial to industrial development initially leads to income inequality, but as per capita income increases, greater income equality follows. The Kuznets curve has attracted significant attention from policymakers and empirical researchers and has been widely applied in environmental studies (Panayotou, 1993; Ota, 2017; Ongan et al., 2021; Husnain et al., 2021).

The main purpose of this study is to test the Kuznets curve for two types of pollution; electronic waste and carbon dioxide. To achieve this, panel data on e-waste generation (available for all OECD developed countries) and carbon dioxide emissions are utilized. The hypothesis being tested is that the relationship between development and pollution follows an inverted U-shaped curve for both e-waste generation and carbon dioxide emissions. The innovation of this article lies in its comparison of the environmental Kuznets curves for both types of pollution, alongside testing the Kuznets hypothesis for e-waste and carbon dioxide emissions.

This article is organized into five sections. After the introduction, the second section presents the literature review. The third section is devoted to the methodology, while the fourth section outlines the model specification and estimation results. The fifth section provides the conclusions and policy implications. References are included at the end of the article.

Literature Review

Grossman and Krueger (1991) were pioneers in examining the relationship between economic growth and environmental degradation. They identified an inverted U-shaped relationship between income and the level of environmental degradation, which, in connection with Kuznets' initial hypothesis, became known as the Environmental Kuznets Curve hypothesis.

Kuznets proposed his hypothesis in such a way that the relationship between GDP per capita and income inequality follows an inverted U-shape (Kuznets, 2019). This hypothesis later became known as the Kuznets hypothesis. According to it, the transition from pre-industrial to industrial development initially leads to income inequality, but as per capita income increases, greater income equality follows. Another implication of the Kuznets hypothesis is that, in the early stages of development, countries tend to prioritize employment and economic growth over environmental concerns (Dasgupta et al., 2002). The Kuznets curve has garnered significant attention from policymakers and researchers and is widely applied in various fields, including environmental economics (Panayotou, 1993; Ota, 2017; Ongan et al., 2021; Husnain et al., 2021) based on the original research of Grossman and Krueger (1991), health economics (Costa-Font et al., 2016) and other areas of macroeconomics. Due to its policy significance, several studies have sought to verify the applicability of the Environmental Kuznets Curve to various economic and environmental issues. Researchers have applied the Kuznets curve to explore the relationship between GDP and various pollution indicators, such as CO₂ (Özokcu & Özdemir, 2017; Alvarado et al., 2018; Lazăr et al., 2019; Shahbaz et al., 2019; Isik et al., 2021; Akadiri et al., 2021), SO₂ (Ridzuan, 2019), NO₂ (Hove & Tursoy, 2019) and particle emissions (Stern & Zha, 2016). Within this framework, other environmental issues, such as industrial wastewater (Wang et al., 2016), deforestation (Culas, 2007), ecological footprint (Ulucak & Bilgili, 2018) and urban solid waste (Gui et al., 2019) have also been examined.

Figure (1) illustrates the Environmental Kuznets Curve. According to this diagram, as economic development begins, pollution levels rise up to a certain point, after which they begin to decline. This non-linear relationship can be explained through scale, technical, and composition effects. First, the expansion of economic activities (scale effect) leads to environmental degradation (Grossman & Krueger, 1991). Then, as the economic structure shifts toward a greater emphasis on the service sector, which typically produces less pollution than the industrial sector, pollution levels decrease. Additionally, technological advancements (technical effect) contribute to reducing environmental damage. As a result, environmental pollution diminishes due to both composition and technical effects (Lin et al., 2016; Alvarez-Herranz et al., 2017). In the early stages of development, however, the unchecked use of resources leads to an increased ecological footprint and higher pollution levels (Sarkodie, 2018), often coupled with weak environmental regulations (Dasgupta et al., 2002). As development progresses, the introduction of clean technologies and innovations, increased environmental awareness, and the strengthening of institutional effectiveness all contribute to reducing environmental pollution (Sarkodie, 2018). Furthermore, public concern (policy effect) leads to stricter environmental regulations, while the willingness to pay for environmentally friendly practices (income effect) rises (Dasgupta et al., 2002), further helping to reduce pollution.

Figure 1. Environmental Kuznets curve (inverted U-Shaped)
Source: Bekhet and Othman (2018)

Regarding the Kuznets curve, various studies have produced differing results. Some studies have identified an inverted U-shaped relationship between economic growth and energy intensity, as seen in the works of Hundie and Daksa (2019) and J. Zhang et al. (2020). This finding aligns with the inverted U-shaped Kuznets curve observed in studies by Ulucak and Bilgili (2018); Vasylieva et al. (2019); Isik et al. (2021) and Akadiri et al. (2021). However, other empirical studies have found a positive relationship between energy intensity and pollution (Aydin & Turan, 2020 and Nathaniel et al., 2021). There are also studies that have found an N-shaped non-linear Kuznets relationship (Sinha Babu & Datta, 2013; Lazăr et al., 2019; Shahbaz et al., 2019), which can be considered a generalization of the inverted U-shaped relationship. Additionally, some studies indicate a U-shaped relationship between economic growth and pollution, as evidenced by Du et al. (2018); S.-C. Xu et al. (2019), Jiang et al. (2020), Ozcan (2013) and Hove and Tursoy (2019). The inverted N-shaped relationship found by Özokcu and Özdemir (2017) can be seen as an extension of the latter U-shaped relationship. While the Kuznets curve is generally found to be non-linear in empirical studies, a few studies have reported an increasing linear relationship (Al-Mulali et al., 2015; Nasir et al., 2019). The differences in the results of empirical studies can be attributed to variations in the choice of environmental indicators. For example, studies focusing on harmful gases such as SO₂, SPM, and CO have found an inverted U-shaped relationship. In contrast, studies on water pollution have yielded both inverted U-shaped and N-shaped relationships. Meanwhile, for pollution indicators such as solid waste and energy, the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) hypothesis has not been confirmed (Bo, 2011).

Despite the sharp increase in e-waste over recent decades, the Environmental Kuznets Curve has primarily been tested for other pollutants, particularly carbon dioxide. This is despite the fact that e-waste has complex characteristics and is growing rapidly. There is substantial evidence of the harmful effects of e-waste. Clarke et al. (2019) found that landfilling one ton of e-waste results in a carbon footprint of 0.02 tons of CO₂. Unrecycled e-waste contributed 0.3% to global warming in 2019 (Forti et al., 2020). Conversely, recycling or reusing one ton of e-waste reduces carbon dioxide emissions by 1.14 and 0.85 tons, respectively (Clarke et al., 2019). Several recent studies have highlighted the impact of e-waste leachate on soil microorganisms (such as bacteria and fungi), as well as other organisms in the ecosystem, including aquatic life, plants, and

humans (Saha et al., 2021). Furthermore, this waste has significantly affected the ecosystems of the Asian and South Asian regions (Priyashantha et al., 2022). A lack of awareness regarding proper disposal methods has led to serious environmental and health issues in developing countries like India, as well as in some developed countries (Gupta & Nath, 2020).

The challenge of waste management, the rapid pace of technological advancement, and the continuous reduction in the lifespan of electronic products are key factors contributing to the growing volume of e-waste (Mihai et al., 2019). While technological progress helps reduce other pollutants, particularly carbon dioxide, it also generates e-waste. Short product life cycles have led to high turnover rates for electronic devices, which, in turn, has increased e-waste generation. These devices have a limited lifespan and are eventually discarded by households. Due to the development, growth, and industrialization of countries, e-waste has become an inseparable part of daily life. As countries continue to grow economically, both the quality and quantity of e-waste change accordingly. E-waste contains harmful compounds that have destructive effects on both human health and the environment. If not managed properly, these substances can persist in nature for long periods, leading to environmental pollution and, in turn, contaminating groundwater resources. This can cause severe and lasting health problems and diseases for humans. Furthermore, improper management and processing of e-waste can result in toxic substances entering the human food chain and the environment through water, air, and soil pollution (Saha et al., 2021).

The fundamental difference between e-waste and other pollutants lies in the fact that modern waste, unlike traditional pollutants, is closely and positively linked to innovation, technology, governance, and the level of development. On the supply side, technological innovation has led to the creation and production of more electronic devices, aimed at enhancing human welfare. On the demand side, rising per capita income and consumer purchasing power have fueled the emergence of new and unlimited human needs. Figure (2) illustrates the product life cycle (PLC).² As shown in the figure, during the product introduction stage, the emergence and development of the product are driven by technological invention and innovation. In the growth stage, the key drivers of product development are increasing domestic and foreign demand, as well as population growth. As the product reaches the end of its life—often due to competition from domestic and international players and the availability of substitute goods—the decline stage begins. However, given the constant and growing demand for electronic devices and the drive for greater profitability, the product life cycle often progresses before the decline stage, with companies continuously releasing updated versions of their products (Figure 2). This ongoing development of electronic products contributes to the growing accumulation of e-waste.

² The product life cycle represents the progression of a product from introduction to decline. This concept is commonly used in marketing, business, and investment. For further reading, see Levitt (1965), BRECHT (2005), and Argente et al. (2024).

Figure 2. Life cycle of electronic products

The continuous life cycle of electronic products, coupled with the ongoing creation and supply of these products, results in the environmental Kuznets curve for e-waste reaching its peak over a longer period. This trend contributes to an increase in the waste generated by electrical and electronic equipment. Simultaneously, many countries face a growing lack of appropriate regulations, social awareness, and institutional capacity to properly dispose of, recycle, and reuse e-waste (Liming Zhang et al., 2019, Shittu et al., 2021, Ravindra & Mor, 2019, Patil & Ramakrishna, 2020). As a result, e-waste has the highest growth rate among municipal solid waste worldwide (Forti et al., 2020). Advanced technology in the production of electronic products has further complicated the management of e-waste. E-waste contains over 1,000 different substances, many of which are hazardous, including lead, mercury, arsenic, cadmium, selenium, chromium, dioxins, and harmful aromatics produced during incineration. These hazardous substances can lead to serious health issues, including acute neurotoxicity, cancer, cardiovascular diseases, liver and kidney failure, and other severe conditions (Ilankoon et al., 2018). The large volume of e-waste causes significant environmental damage due to its toxic and complex structure, which is difficult to separate. Metals such as iron, copper, aluminum, and gold, along with non-metallic materials, account for about 60.2% of the total weight of e-waste, while other pollutants make up approximately 39.8% of its weight (Vats & Singh, 2014).³

The less apparent nature and relatively low visibility of e-waste (similar to space debris) compared to other pollutants make society less sensitive to it. As a result, governance often gives lower priority to this type of waste. In fact, good governance, in terms of promoting economic welfare, can lead to the development of more electronic

³ Thus, e-waste contains valuable materials such as iron, aluminum, copper, gold, and other useful components (Morf et al., 2013). The primary motivation for waste management, beyond environmental concerns, is the fact that e-waste holds significant quantities of precious and valuable materials (Liming Zhang et al., 2019).

products, which in turn generates more e-waste. Consumption habits also contribute to the growing volume of electronic waste. For instance, people may continue to hold on to old mobile phones even after they have reached the end of their lifespan, or they may dispose of e-waste with regular household waste (Babayemi et al., 2017).

The role of government in the creation of e-waste can also be examined through the lens of political economy theories. Two dominant theories in this regard are the median voter theory (or consensus hypothesis) and the partisan theory (Arslan et al., 2024). Of Environmental issues, of course, are not inherently tied to any particular political party or group. What matters is the public's stance on the environment, with political parties shaping their policies to align with public opinion in order to gain votes and retain power. The ideology of a party is often aligned with a particular set of environmental policies, which in turn have different impacts on the environment. For instance, left-wing parties typically focus on improving environmental quality, while right-wing parties tend to leave environmental issues to be addressed by market mechanisms. Given that most European governments are right-wing, it appears that the nature of e-waste allows governments to prioritize economic welfare over addressing the environmental challenges associated with its pollution. Cahan et al. (2019) indicate that OECD member countries, with an average score of 2.94, generally lean toward right-wing political ideologies. Therefore, it would not be surprising to observe an increase in e-waste in these countries.

Regarding the positive impact of technology, Vishwakarma et al. (2023) highlight how the technological revolution in electronic equipment has transformed human lifestyles. These products (EEE) often include household appliances, entertainment systems, security devices, and medical equipment, with newer electronic products being rapidly integrated into daily life. Numerous examples illustrate the positive impact of technology on e-waste, such as the rise of smart devices and innovations in mobile phones with high-speed internet. Interestingly, the shift to more advanced technology compels consumers to adopt newer devices, as new equipment is often incompatible with older technology. Yousufi (2023) also attributes the increasing and continuous generation of e-waste to technological development, which is driven by people's growing demand for electrical and electronic products. Meanwhile, the shortening of product life cycles has further contributed to the accumulation of e-waste.

The environmental damage caused by e-waste can also be analyzed within the framework of the business model. As Yousufi (2023) points out, traditional linear business models are based on the production and consumption of goods, assuming unlimited resources, which leads to environmental problems. To address this limitation, socio-technical system transitions are incorporated into these models. With this modification (production, consumption, waste), each economy attempts to design its own version of a circular economy (CE). However, all these systems share a common challenge: they must contend with resource scarcity, waste leakage, and pollution emissions. Despite these challenges, these systems all feature regenerative and restorative qualities.

Figure (3) illustrates the material balance for a given Circular Economy (CE) model (Pearce & Turner, 1989). The diagram consists of four main components: amenity values, resources, sinks for residuals, and the life support system. As shown in the diagram,

resources (both renewable and exhaustible) are used in the economic system for production. The produced goods are then consumed, contributing to welfare and utility values. However, part of the resources, along with production and consumption, is converted into waste and residues. In the case of recycling, the waste is reintegrated into the system for reuse in the production process. If the detrimental effects of waste outweigh the welfare benefits, it negatively impacts utility. Using this system, electronic waste can be distinguished from other pollutants due to its short lifespan, low visibility (non-polluting appearance), growing and accelerating consumption, and the technology-intensive nature of electronic products. In this context, a mechanism must be in place to address the material imbalance within the life support system. Without such a mechanism, the growing challenges of electronic waste will exacerbate sustainable development issues. If sustainable development is considered a concern for future generations, it could influence the direction of the Kuznets curve and reduce its slope for this type of pollution.

Figure 3. Material Balance

Reference: Present study based on Pearce and Turner (1989)

Considerable efforts have been made in terms of legislation, regulations, and policy to address e-waste. One of the initial steps occurred in 1988 when Italy dumped 4,000 tons of toxic waste in Nigeria. In response, Nigeria passed a law criminalizing the transport, storage, import, purchase, and sale of toxic waste (Perkins et al., 2014). Nigeria played a key role in the Basel Convention and was the first African country to sign the agreement. Since then, various initiatives have been launched to raise awareness about the human consequences of e-waste. Additionally, the number of international organizations advocating for the control and recycling of e-waste continues to grow. UN bodies, particularly the World Health Organization, have conducted studies to assess the human impact of e-waste. The organization's first report (WHO, 2021) highlighted alarming statistics on the number of women and children exposed to the toxicity of e-waste.

For the management of e-waste, the 3Rs principles—Reuse, Reduce, and Recycle—have been proposed, emphasizing the responsibility of producers through the concept of Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR). The OECD defines EPR as an environmental policy approach in which the producer’s responsibility for a product extends to its post-consumer life cycle stage (OECD, 2001). The Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) approach can also be used to monitor and track the process of e-waste generation from cradle to grave. Despite these initiatives and approaches, in 2019, 53.6 million tons of e-waste were generated globally, and this figure is projected to rise significantly to 74 million tons by 2030 (Murthy & Ramakrishna, 2022). According to the WHO (2021), only 17.4 percent of e-waste was collected and recycled in 2019. This is concerning, as both the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) have emphasized environmental sustainability.⁴ For instance, Goal 7 of the MDGs focuses on ensuring environmental sustainability, while Goal 8 aims to create a global partnership for development. Various SDGs also address the issue, such as Goal 3 (Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages), Goal 9 (Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive, and sustainable industrialization), Goal 15 (Protect, restore, and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems), Goal 16 (Promote peaceful and inclusive societies for sustainable development), and Goal 17 (Strengthen the means of implementation and revitalize the global partnership). Despite the efforts of international institutions, laws, and regulations, as well as global initiatives, it seems that e-waste, with its rapid growth, will continue to be one of the most pressing challenges for sustainable development in the future.

Building on the literature above and Stern (2017) research, the differences in environmental Kuznets curves—where conventional pollution generally follows an inverted U-shape, while e-waste likely follows a U-shape—can be explained through scale, composition, and technical effects. First, the scale effect refers to the increase in production as a result of economies of scale. Given the growing and high demand for electronic products, this effect can lead to increased production and exports, thereby generating more e-waste. On the demand side, due to the low visibility of e-waste pollution, consumer preferences and utility tend to focus more on consumption rather than environmental impact. Second, the composition effect, which relates to the changing mix of industries during development, plays a role in the spread of e-waste. This effect, influenced by comparative advantages, leads to greater production of electrical and electronic equipment (EEE) in more developed countries, contributing to higher e-waste generation. Finally, the technical effect involves changes in the production process, such as input substitution (shifts in the mix of materials used) and technological advancements in production, which impact the pollution intensity per unit of output or input. The invisibility of e-waste pollution is particularly evident here, as many electronic products contain hazardous materials like batteries, power cords, circuit boards, plastic housings, cathode ray tubes, and lead capacitors. The pollution associated with these items only becomes apparent after the product’s life ends, and if they are not properly recycled. Given these factors, it is highly unlikely that an Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) would emerge for e-waste.

⁴ For MDG and SDG see Halisçelik and Soytaş (2019)

Despite the significance of e-waste pollution, the literature on the Kuznets curve generally focuses on pollution from fossil fuels (Table 1). Meanwhile, new forms of pollution, such as electronic waste, are emerging during the process of economic development. In this context, e-waste has notably increased in developed OECD countries (Rasekhi & Khodamolhosseini, 2023). Researchers and policymakers recognize that the rapid rise in e-waste presents substantial risks to the environment, economy, and human health (Parajuly et al., 2020; Singh et al., 2020; Y. Xu et al., 2020). As a result, the challenges associated with the proper management of electronic waste are considerable (Cole et al., 2019).

As shown in Table (1), studies on waste pollution within the framework of the Environmental Kuznets Curve have predominantly focused on traditional waste types. For instance, Ercolano et al. (2018) examined the Kuznets curve hypothesis for municipal solid waste in 1,497 municipalities in the Lombardy region of Italy between 2005 and 2011 using panel data methods. This study found an inverted U-shaped relationship between waste generation and economic development. Madden et al. (2019) tested the Waste Kuznets Curve (WKC) hypothesis for New South Wales, Australia, from 2011 to 2015 using spatial econometrics and found evidence supporting the WKC hypothesis. Gui et al. (2019) explored urban solid waste production in 285 Chinese cities between 2006 and 2015 using spatial panel data methods, concluding that economic growth leads to increased waste generation. Yilmaz (2020) examined the Kuznets curve for OECD municipal solid waste during the period from 2002 to 2017. Using panel data methods, the study identified an inverted U-shaped relationship for OECD countries, though this relationship was only observed in relative terms. Additionally, consumption was found to be a key driver of waste production. Boubellouta and Kusch-Brandt (2020) confirmed the e-waste Kuznets curve hypothesis for 30 European countries (EU28+2) from 2000 to 2016, using the generalized method of moments (GMM) and two-stage least squares (2SLS). Bao and Lu (2023) examined the Environmental Kuznets Curve for construction waste using panel data from 27 European economies, with results confirming an inverted U-shaped relationship between GDP per capita and construction waste generation.

Overall, several empirical studies have highlighted the key role of income in waste generation (Johnstone & Labonne, 2004; Vieira & Matheus, 2018; Namlis & Komilis, 2019). Some of these studies have confirmed the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) hypothesis between income and waste generation (Arbulú et al., 2015; Yilmaz, 2020). However, other studies, such as those by Mazzanti (2008) and Baalbaki and Marrouch (2020) did not confirm this hypothesis. According to Namlis and Komilis (2019) income and social development drive increased demand for electronic appliances, which in turn leads to a rise in electronic waste. Similarly, urban solid waste grows with rapid population growth and urbanization, which may offset the diminishing effect of per capita income. On the other hand, Aldieri et al. (2019), argue that strong knowledge spillovers in waste recycling and environmental innovations play a critical role in the formation of the Kuznets curve (Gardiner & Hajek, 2020). Innovation can help mitigate the external effects of waste by developing systems for waste-to-energy conversion and recycling (Pan et al., 2015; AlQattan et al., 2018). Furthermore, education has been shown to reduce urban solid waste (Gu et al., 2015; Mattar et al., 2018).

Table 1. Empirical Studies of Environmental Kuznets Curve

Authors, Year	Variables of EKC	Limits of research	Model	dependent variable (vertical axis)	independent variable (horizontal axis)	Research results
Ulucak & Bilgili, 2018	Economic growth and pollution	High, middle, low-income countries 2000-2015	CUP-FM and CUP-BC	Environmental footprint (per capita)	GDP (at constant prices)	inverted U-shaped
Vasylieva et al., 2019	Economic growth and pollution	European Union and Ukraine 2000-2016	FMOLS and DOLS	Greenhouse gas emissions per capita (Kilo tons)	GDP per capita (US\$)	inverted U-shaped
Isik et al., 2021	Economic growth and pollution	8 OECD countries 1962-2015	CCEMG and Fixed effects	CO2 emissions (tons per capita)	logarithm of real GDP per capita	inverse U-shaped
Akadiri et al., 2021	Economic growth and pollution	BRICS 1995-2018	Panel data	CO2 emission (million metric tons)	GDP (2010 US\$) and economic freedom index	inverse U-shaped
Ozcan, 2013	Economic growth and pollution	12 countries of the Middle East 1990-2008	Panel data	CO2 emissions (metric tons per capita)	Real GDP per capita (US\$)	U-shaped
Hove & Tursoy, 2019	Economic growth and pollution	24 emerging economies 2000-2017	GMM	CO2 emission growth (metric tons per capita), fossil fuel consumption growth (percentage of total) and nitrogen oxide gas	GDP growth per capita (constant 2010 US\$)	U-shaped

Authors, Year	Variables of EKC	Limits of research	Model	dependent variable (vertical axis)	independent variable (horizontal axis)	Research results
				emissions (thousand tons per capita)		
Al-Mulali et al., 2015	Economic growth and pollution	Vietnam 1981-2011	ARDL	Logarithm of CO2 emissions per capita (million metric tons)	Logarithm of GDP per capita (US\$)	Linear increasing
Nasir et al., 2019	Economic growth and pollution	5 selected economies of ASEAN 1982-2014	DOLS and FMOLS	CO2 emissions (metric tons per capita)	GDP growth rate	Linear increasing
Sinha Babu & Datta, 2013	Per capita income and pollution	22 developing countries from the three regions of Asia, Latin America and sub-Saharan Africa	Panel data (fixed effects)	Environmental quality indicators	Per capita income and development balance index	N-shaped
Lazăr et al., 2019	Economic growth and pollution	11 countries from Eastern and Central Europe 1996-2015	AMG MG MG-FMOLS	CO2 emissions (per capita)	GDP (based on purchasing power parity)	N-shaped
Shahbaz et al., 2019	Economic growth and pollution	Vietna 1974-2016	Time series	Logarithm of CO2 emissions (metric tons)	Logarithm of GDP (\$US)	N-shaped

Authors, Year	Variables of EKC	Limits of research	Model	dependent variable (vertical axis)	independent variable (horizontal axis)	Research results
Özokcu & Özdemir, 2017	Economic growth and pollution	26 OECD countries, 52 emerging countries, 1980-2010	Panel data (Fixed effects)	Logarithm of CO2 emissions per capita	Logarithm of GDP	Inverted N-shaped
Ercolano et al., 2018	Economic development and urban solid waste generation	Lombardy region of Italy 2005-2011	Panel data (Fixed and random effects)	Daily waste generation per capita	economic development (income)	inverted U-shaped
Madden et al., 2019	Socio-economic factors and waste	New South Wales region of Australia 2011-2015	Spatial Econometrics	Production of municipal waste per capita (kg/person)	Logarithm of average household income (\$)	inverted U-shaped
Yılmaz, 2020	Economic growth and waste	OECD 2002-2017	GMM	Per capita logarithmic generation of municipal solid waste	Logarithm of GDP per capita	Linear increasing
Alvarado et al., 2018	Economic growth and pollution	151 countries with high, middle, low income 1980-2016	Panel data (Fixed and random effects)	Logarithm of CO2 emissions	Logarithm of real production per capita	inverted U-shaped

Given the rapidly increasing generation of electrical and electronic equipment, the low visibility and subtle effects of e-waste, and the urgent need for both global and national strategies to sustainably manage this type of pollution, the present study aims to address the limited literature on the e-waste Kuznets curve. It explores the e-waste Kuznets curve, compares it with the environmental Kuznets curves for carbon dioxide, and contributes to filling the theoretical and empirical gap in the existing research.

Methodology

The main purpose of this research is to examine the environmental Kuznets curve for two types of pollution: electronic waste and carbon dioxide. To achieve this, data from 28 European countries are analyzed, including Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Switzerland, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, the United Kingdom, Greece, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Norway, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Slovak Republic, Slovenia, and Sweden. Based on existing literature, the hypotheses are tested using the equations (1) and (2), estimated through panel data methods for the selected countries during the period from 2002 to 2020. The explanatory variables in these equations include GDP per capita and its square, exports of information and communication technology goods, population, economic structure, governance, and technology, with their corresponding data provided in Table (2).

$$WEEE_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta_1 GDP_{it} + \alpha_2 GDP_{it}^2 + \alpha_3 ICT_{it} + \alpha_4 POP_{it} + \alpha_5 IND_{it} + \alpha_6 WGI_{it} + \alpha_7 TEC_{it} + u_{it} \quad (1)$$

$$CO_{2it} = b_i + \beta_1 GDP_{it} + \beta_2 GDP_{it}^2 + \beta_3 ICT_{it} + \beta_4 POP_{it} + \beta_5 IND_{it} + \beta_6 TEC_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (2)$$

In these equations, $WEEE_{it}$ represents electronic waste generation, CO_{2it} denotes carbon dioxide emission, GDP_{it} refers to gross domestic product per capita, GDP_{it}^2 is the square of gross domestic product per capita, ICT_{it} represents export of information and communication technology goods, POP_{it} stands for population, IND_{it} indicates economic structure, WGI_{it} is the governance index, TEC_{it} represents technology, all for country i in year t .

Table 2. Introduction of variables

Variable	Measurement	Source
$WEEE_{it}$	Total of 6 types of electronic waste (in kilograms per capita)	Urban Mine Platform
CO_{2it}	Carbon dioxide emissions (in metric tons per capita)	World Bank
GDP_{it}	GDP per capita (constant 2015 US\$)	World Bank
ICT_{it}	ICT goods exports (% of total goods exports)	World Bank
POP_{it}	Population	World Bank
IND_{it}	Industrial value added (constant 2015 US\$) to GDP (constant 2015 US\$)	World Bank
WGI_{it}	Average WGI	Worldwide Governance Indicators (WGI)
TEC_{it}	The share of medium and high technology exports in industrial exports	UNIDO

Table (3) provides the description of the variables. According to the table, the average electronic waste generation is 16.30 kg per capita, while carbon dioxide emissions average 7.57 tons per capita. Electronic waste ranges from 4.44 to 30.44 kg per capita, whereas carbon dioxide emissions fluctuate between 3.18 and 25.61 tons per capita.

Table 3. Variables Description

Variable	Unit	Min	Max	Median	Average	Standard deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
WEEE	kg per capita	4.44	30.44	16.53	16.30	5.31	-0.04	-0.56
CO ₂	Metric tons per capita	3.18	25.61	7.16	7.57	3.38	2.19	7.44
GDP	constant 2015 US\$	4263.98	112417.88	28866.74	34486.86	23496.39	1.22	1.23
ICT	% of total goods exports	0.79	31.07	4.07	6.33	5.54	1.62	2.46
POP	person	446175	83160871	8288941.50	17723286.80	22787378.34	1.60	1.14
IND	No units	0.10	0.40	0.24	0.24	0.06	0.04	0.28
WGI	No units	0.08	1.95	1.07	1.12	0.48	-0.16	-1.09
TEC	No units	0.17	0.79	0.55	0.54	0.12	-0.37	-0.26

Model Specification and Estimation Results

As mentioned, equations (1) and (2) are used to test the Kuznets curves in the present study. Before estimating these equations, the cross-sectional dependence was first tested, and accordingly, the second-generation stationary test was applied. The results of both tests are presented in Table (4).

Table 4. Pesaran's Cross-sectional dependence test and CIPS Unit Root test

Variable	Pesaran CD test	P. value	Test result	CIPS Unit Root test	Test result
WEEE	82.89430	0.0000	cross-section dependence	-2.37232	Not All variables are stationary
CO ₂	52.73656	0.0000		-1.87043	
GDP	54.25838	0.0000		-1.41051	
GDP ²	54.24751	0.0000		-1.33337	
ICT	20.28201	0.0000		-1.65269	
POP	7.315450	0.0000		-2.17337	
IND	27.77819	0.0000		-1.80251	
WGI	6.271560	0.0000		-1.53244	
TEC	14.75801	0.0000		-1.66645	

The ordinary least squares (OLS) model for cross-sectional time series (panel) data faces issues such as correlated errors and heteroscedasticity. To address these problems, Parks (1967) suggested using generalized least squares (GLS) (Beck & Katz, 1995). The GLS estimator for panel data allows estimation in the presence of autocorrelation within panels and cross-sectional correlation and/or heteroscedasticity across panels. However, since Parks' method may lead to an underestimation of parameter variability (Beck & Katz, 1995), the feasible generalized least squares (FGLS) method is employed, which assumes the error structure is known rather than estimated. Additionally, many linear models with serially correlated errors (e.g., AR(1) errors) and various linear mixed models can be fitted using FGLS (Olive & Olive, 2017). For this reason, diagnostic tests are not required because FGLS itself provides a solution. The FGLS method also enhances the precision and reliability of the estimates compared to OLS.

In the next step, to ensure that the regression results are not spurious, we use the Kao test. Additionally, to determine whether to use fixed or random effects, a Hausman test is performed. Based on the results presented in Table (5), the fixed effects model is confirmed. Finally, heteroscedasticity is tested using the modified Wald test, and serial autocorrelation is tested with the Wooldridge test. The results of these tests, shown in Table (5), confirm the presence of both heteroscedasticity and serial autocorrelation at the 99% confidence level.

Table 5. Kao test, Hausman test, Modified Wald's heteroskedasticity test and Wooldridge's autocorrelation test

Test	Model	Statistics	P. value	Test result
Kao test	(1)	-2.4577	0.0070	The existence of cointegration between variables
	(2)	2.3788	0.0087	
Hausman test	(1)	468.49	0.0000	Fixed effects
	(2)	80.19	0.0000	
Modified Wald test	(1)	573.90	0.0000	Existence of heteroskedasticity
	(2)	9171.70	0.0000	
Wooldridge test	(1)	2175.756	0.0000	Existence of autocorrelation
	(2)	59.447	0.0000	

Given the presence of heteroscedasticity and serial autocorrelation, the research model is estimated using the feasible generalized least squares (FGLS) method for panel data. The results are presented in Table (6).

Table 6. Estimation Results

Model	Model 1 (dependent variable: Electronic waste)		Model 2 (dependent variable: Carbon dioxide)	
Variable	Estimated coefficients	P> z	Estimated coefficients	P> z
GDP	0.0003535	0.000	0.000137	0.000
GDP ²	-1.98e-09	0.000	-1.06e-09	0.000
ICT	-0.0507684	0.000	0.0271794	0.021
POP	5.74e-08	0.000	-1.47e-08	0.028
IND	-15.79381	0.000	9.432874	0.000
WGI	-1.416736	0.000	-	-
TEC	2.86872	0.006	-2.316354	0.001
Constant	9.807176	0.000	3.527344	0.000
Wald chi2	227.89	0.0000	88.10	0.0000

As shown in Table (6), the environmental Kuznets curve for electronic waste follows an inverted U-shape. This finding aligns with the results of Ercolano et al. (2018), Madden et al. (2019) and Boubellouta and Kusch-Brandt (2020). The threshold level of GDP per capita at which the Kuznets curve for waste generation begins to decline is estimated at \$89,267.68 (Figure 4). This threshold is reasonable and consistent with the findings of Madden et al. (2019) and Boubellouta and Kusch-Brandt (2020). The estimated threshold falls within the GDP per capita range of three countries—Norway, Switzerland, and Luxembourg. However, most European countries remain below this threshold.

Figure 4. E-waste generation per capita and GDP per capita for 28 selected European countries

Other results from the estimation of equation 1 indicate that technological development leads to an increase in e-waste. This finding is logical, as technological advancements introduce more sophisticated electronic devices. The results also show that the export of information and communication technology goods has a negative effect on e-waste generation, which aligns with the findings of Boubellouta and Kusch-Brandt (2020). According to the results, good governance helps reduce e-waste, suggesting that European governments are addressing the issue of electronic waste generation and accumulation. The positive effect of population growth on e-waste generation observed in this study is consistent with the findings of Chen (2018), Boubellouta and Kusch-Brandt (2020) and Zambrano-Monserrate et al. (2021). Conversely, the effect of economic structure (industrial share) on e-waste is negative and significant, possibly reflecting the dominance of the technology sector, which tends to generate less e-waste.

To further analyze the results, Table (7) presents the quartile intervals of e-waste recycling for selected countries during the time period 2013-2021, based on the most recent available data. As seen in the table, European countries, perhaps due to the reasons mentioned earlier, have yet to fully recognize the negative impacts of e-waste or have not prioritized addressing the issue. The table clearly shows that most of the studied European countries fall within the lower quartiles. Consequently, many countries are positioned in

the lower half of the Kuznets curve and are still experiencing an increase in e-waste. Additionally, countries located near the threshold of the curve tend to have higher quartile indices and show growth in e-waste recycling.

Table 7. Quartile intervals for recycled e-waste in European countries over the period 2013-2021

CON	RW2013	RW2016	RW2020	RW2021
FIN	U	U	U	U
LUX	UL	UL	U	U
SVK	UL	U	U	U
CZE	U	U	U	U
HRV	U	U	U	U
PRT	UL	L	L	U
BGR	UL	L	LU	U
NOR	LU	UL	U	UL
CYP	LU	U	U	LU
DEU	LU	UL	UL	UL
SVN	L	L	UL	UL
ITA	U	UL	UL	UL
LTU	L	LU	LU	UL
LVA	U	U	LU	UL
AUT	L	L	LU	LU
IRL	UL	LU	UL	LU
EST	L	UL	L	LU
GRC	U	UL	LU	LU
POL	L	LU	UL	LU
FRA	L	L	L	L
DNK	LU	UL	LU	L
NLD	LU	L	L	L
BEL	L	L	L	L
SWE	UL	LU	L	L
ESP	LU	U	UL	L
HUN	U	LU	L	L

As shown in Table (6), the environmental Kuznets curve for carbon dioxide follows an inverted U-shape. The threshold level for this curve is \$64,622.64, which is lower than the threshold for the e-waste curve (Figure 5). The threshold level for carbon dioxide in this study aligns with the findings of Akadiri et al. (2021) and Isik et al. (2021). Three countries—Norway, Switzerland, and Luxembourg—are positioned to the right of the threshold, while the other countries in the study have yet to reach this threshold.

Figure 5. Carbon dioxide emissions per capita and GDP per capita for 28 selected European countries

Other results from the estimation of equation 2 show that the structure of the economy (industrial share) has led to higher carbon dioxide emissions, indicating the dependence of these industries on fossil fuels. The study also finds that the export of information and communication technology goods contributes to increased carbon dioxide emissions, likely due to a rise in energy-intensive industrial production. These findings align with the research by Rasekhi and Ghanbartabar (2024). Additionally, the results indicate that an increase in population leads to a decrease in carbon dioxide emissions, which could reflect the overall development of these societies. Furthermore, the study shows that technological progress has improved environmental quality. This is logical, as advanced technologies that are energy-efficient, environmentally friendly, and lower in energy consumption contribute to a cleaner environment (Paramati et al., 2022).

Table (8) presents the quartile intervals of the Environmental Performance Index for the European countries studied from 2013 to 2021, based on the latest available data. This index ranks countries by the effectiveness of their governments' environmental policies, considering factors such as citizens' health, resource consumption, pollution, and species extinction, with a particular emphasis on air pollution. The table highlights that most of the selected European countries fall within the lower quartiles. As a result, many are positioned in the lower half of the Kuznets curve and continue to experience rising carbon dioxide levels. Additionally, countries near the threshold of the curve tend to have higher quartile indices. The table supports the conclusion that most of the studied countries are situated in the left half of the environmental Kuznets curve.

Table 8. Quartile intervals for EPI in European countries over the period 2010-2020

CON	EPI2010	EPI2016	EPI2020
LUX	LU	LU	U
GBR	UL	UL	U
FRA	U	UL	U
FIN	U	U	U
DNK	LU	U	U
CHE	U	UL	U
AUT	U	UL	U
SWE	U	U	UL
SVN	L	U	LU
SVK	U	LU	LU
PRT	UL	U	LU
POL	L	L	L
NOR	U	UL	UL
NLD	LU	L	UL
LVA	UL	LU	L
LTU	LU	LU	L
ITA	UL	L	LU
IRL	LU	UL	UL
HUN	LU	LU	L
HRV	LU	UL	L
GRC	L	LU	LU
EST	L	U	LU
ESP	UL	U	UL
DEU	UL	L	UL
CZE	UL	LU	LU
CYP	L	L	L
BGR	L	L	L
BEL	L	L	UL

Overall, the results of this study confirm the inverted U-shaped environmental Kuznets curve hypothesis for both e-waste pollution and carbon dioxide emissions in European countries. Additionally, the estimation results from equations 1 and 2 indicate that the threshold level for the e-waste Kuznets curve is higher than that for the carbon dioxide Kuznets curve. Moreover, the study's calculations suggest that the trend of increasing e-waste is accelerating more rapidly than that of carbon dioxide emissions. This implies that the accumulation of e-waste is becoming an increasingly significant challenge for the future of developed societies.

Conclusions and Policy Implications

This study aims to investigate the Kuznets curve hypothesis for e-waste and carbon dioxide emissions and compare the two curves across 28 selected European countries

from 2002 to 2020. The findings, based on estimations using the generalized least squares method, confirm the environmental Kuznets hypothesis for both types of pollution. The threshold level for the carbon dioxide Kuznets curve is estimated at \$64,622.64, which is lower than the threshold level for the e-waste Kuznets curve (\$89,267.68).

Findings from this study indicate that exports of ICT goods, economic structure, and governance have contributed to reducing e-waste generation, while technological advancement and population growth have led to an increase in this type of pollution. Conversely, the study estimates that technological progress and population growth have helped reduce carbon dioxide emissions, whereas exports of ICT goods and economic structure have contributed to increased air pollution.

Although this study focuses on selected European countries, carbon dioxide pollution, due to its movement through air and water, has become a global issue, requiring coordinated international efforts for effective mitigation. Additionally, the higher growth rate of e-waste production, coupled with rising per capita generation, suggests that e-waste is becoming an increasingly serious problem. Thus, policies promoting environmentally friendly technologies are essential, not only for addressing carbon dioxide emissions but also for managing e-waste. Extending the lifespan of electronic devices—despite potential conflicts with industry profitability—could play a key role in reducing e-waste. Alongside technological reforms and improvements in governance, global environmental governance is also necessary.

Key recommendations from this study include improving governance indicators, expanding e-waste recycling programs, fostering regional cooperation, implementing stringent technology and environmental standards, supporting green technologies, strengthening international institutions to enforce global environmental standards, and designing a structured international energy transition. Governments should be required to enhance collection and recycling initiatives, impose green taxes and penalties on non-compliant producers, and use these financial resources to encourage green innovation and improve environmental quality.

In summary, this study advocates for the design of a comprehensive framework for environmental standards that considers all forms of pollution. By implementing such a system, resource balance can be optimized to maximize sustainable welfare.

Author Contributions

The corresponding author contributed to conceptualization, idea generation, article content quality, research finalization and control of all calculations and estimations of the research model. The second author was responsible for the empirical literature, initial estimation of the research model, and initial framework of the article.

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